

Research and Innovation

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Research and Innovation, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Summary Innovation Index” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data for Kosovo* not available

Source
European Innovation Scoreboard 2024. EU countries and neighbouring countries database https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard_en#eis-interactive-tool (accessed 10 February 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

WB Steering Platform on R&I meetings		
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Supporting Western Balkans' reforms for science and research alignment with the EU acquis Participation in European programmes, initiatives and schemes					
Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Technical assistance to Chapter 25 (Science and Research)				
Albania	Low level of bilateral R&D projects and Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions				
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of bilateral R&D projects, Twinning projects and TAIEX missions				
Kosovo	Low level of bilateral R&D projects and Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions				
Montenegro	Low level of bilateral R&D projects and Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions				
North Macedonia	Low level of bilateral R&D projects and Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions				
Serbia	Increased number of bilateral R&D projects, Twinning projects and TAIEX missions				

Legend:

Information not available				
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Highlights

Strong participation of the Western Balkans in the 2024 EIT Jumpstarter Cohort
Improving innovation support and trans-national R&I cooperation by continuous growth of the EIT Community

